

**ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ РЕТИНОЇДУ ТА САЛІЦИЛОВОЇ
КИСЛОТИ У ЛІКУВАННІ РІЗНИХ ГІСТОЛОГІЧНИХ ТИПІВ
СЕБОРЕЙНОГО КЕРАТОЗУ
EFFICACY OF RETINOID AND SALICYLIC ACID IN THE
TREATMENT OF DIFFERENT HISTOLOGICAL TYPES OF
SEBORRHEIC KERATOSIS**

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Introduction. Seborrheic keratosis (SK) is a benign neoplasm of the skin, characterized by a high prevalence in the population, especially among middle-aged and elderly people. The lack of clinical guidelines for the treatment of this dermatosis contributes to the creation of recommended essences for the tactics of such patients. A particularly pressing issue is the use of topical dosage forms that can provide a sufficient level of efficacy and compliance. Given that keratinization disorders are the basis for the occurrence of keratosis, topical retinoids can control the processes of keratinocyte differentiation and keratinization. Therefore, their appointment may be predominant for local treatment of SK.

Material and methods. On the basis of the "University Clinic," ZSMU and the Department of Dermatovenerology and Cosmetology with the Course of Aesthetic Medicine of FPE have examined 35 patients with SK. Verification of the diagnosis required clinical, dermatoscopic, and histopathological examination to determine the morphological type of keratosis. Additionally, an ultrasound scan of the SK (Dub cutis 33 MHz - Germany) was performed to determine the tumor's thickness. As a retinoid, adapalene gel was used twice a day for 2 weeks, and an additional 5% salicylic ointment was prescribed twice a week, once in the evening (instead of adapalene gel).

Results. According to the pathomorphological study, 19 cases (54%) were acanthotic, 13 (37%) papillomatous, 2 (6%) reticular, and 1 (3%) irritated. The average thickness of the SK represented by the papillomatous variant was 0.986 ± 0.176 mm. For the acanthotic type, this value averaged 0.686 ± 0.272 mm, and for the reticular and irritated 0.479 ± 0.044 mm and 0.444 mm, respectively. After a repeat

ultrasound examination of the foci, it was determined that all SK with papillomatous patterns changed in the direction of thinning by an average of 0.075 ± 0.12 mm. While among 19 acanthotic patterns, demonstration of response to topical treatment was recorded in only 12 cases. The average thinning in the acanthotic group is 0.081 ± 0.03 mm. According to ultrasound scans: 7 (36.8%) representatives of the acanthotic type, all irritated and reticular (100%) - did not respond to topical therapy with retinoids and keratolytic.

Conclusions. Thus, papillomatous and most acanthotic patterns of SK are most sensitive to the use of topical retinoids, which is demonstrated by a decrease in their thickness. This, in turn, may indicate more significant changes in the level of terminal differentiation and keratinization for these morphotypes of keratosis.